

Mathematical Model for Solving Transportation Problems Using Linear Programming During Highway Construction

Mudimadugula Pavankumar¹ and Makendran C²

^{1,2}National Institute of Technology, Tiruchirappalli, India

Abstract Transportation problems involve optimizing the allocation of resources from suppliers to demand points, with various constraints and costs. This study presents a comprehensive comparative analysis of mathematical linear programming (LP) models for solving transportation problems in highway projects with traditional operational research techniques, and CPLEX software. The study assesses the efficiency, accuracy, and scalability of these two methods in addressing real-world transportation challenges. In this paper, employed conventional operational research methods like Vogels Approximation method (VAM) and Modified distribution method (MODI). A comparative analysis is based on performance metrics, including solution quality, computation time, and resource utilization. The findings reveal valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of each approach, helping decision-makers choose the most suitable method for addressing transportation problems in different contexts. The study also contributes to the ongoing discussion of optimization techniques for logistics and supply chain management.

Keywords Transportation problems, linear programming, operational research, CPLEX software, optimization, logistics, supply chain management

Introduction

Logistics Management in greenfield highways is the process of planning, organizing and controlling the movement of goods and services on highways that are built on land that has not been previously developed for transportation purposes. Logistics Management in Greenfield Highway includes materials transport, equipment logistics, site access and traffic control, supply chain coordination, storage and inventory management, environmental considerations and cost control. It involves the integration of all the activities necessary to get the right material, to the right place, at the right time, in the right condition and at the right cost. Effective logistics in Greenfield highways is crucial for on-time, on-budget project completion with minimal disruptions to the surrounding area. Highway projects are complex undertakings that involve the transportation of large quantities of materials over long distances. Transportation costs can significantly impact the overall cost of a highway project, making it crucial to optimize transportation planning and execution. Mathematical linear programming (LP) models have emerged as powerful tools for solving transportation problems in highway projects. LP models provide a structured framework for representing and optimizing transportation costs, taking into account factors such as transportation distances, transportation modes, and transportation capacities. Conventional operational research methods, such as the transportation simplex method and Vogel's approximation method, have traditionally been used to solve transportation problems. These methods are straightforward and relatively easy to implement, making them suitable for small-scale problems. However, they may encounter computational challenges when dealing with large-scale transportation problems with a significant number of variables and constraints. CPLEX is a commercial optimization software package that offers a variety of optimization algorithms, including LP solvers. CPLEX is particularly well-suited for solving large-scale LP problems, employing efficient optimization algorithms that can handle complex constraints and a large number of variables. CPLEX provides a user-friendly interface and can be integrated with various programming languages, making it a versatile tool for transportation optimization in highway projects.

Literature review

S Choudhari and Tindwani (2017), discussed the importance of logistics optimization in road construction projects. The authors argue that logistics costs can account for up to 25% of the total project cost, and that optimization can lead to significant savings. They propose a linear programming (LP) model to optimize the material logistics of a road construction project. The model takes into account the following factors: quantity and type of materials required, location of the borrow pits and construction sites, The transportation costs, the constraints on the availability of materials and equipment. Sanyuan Niu, Yi Yang, and Wei Pan (2019) proposed an integrated platform designed for planning, optimizing, and visualizing logistics in modular integrated construction (MIC) projects. The platform combines building information modeling (BIM), geographical information system (GIS), and vehicle routing problem (VRP) algorithms. The BIM model extracts geometric and topological information of modules and installation schedules. GIS data represents the road network and other geographical features, while the VRP algorithm determines optimal routes for module transportation from the factory to the construction site. The platform generates a 3D visualization of the logistics scenario, enabling the assessment of proposed routes and identification of potential issues. A case study in Hong Kong validates the platform, demonstrating its capability to produce efficient and feasible logistics solutions. Ghourrassi et al(2017), argue that customer satisfaction hinges on effective warehouse and inventory management solutions, seamless supply

chain integration within the company's operational framework, efficient Information Communication Technology (ICT) process sharing and management, coordinated handling of common key performance indicators (KPIs) and performance data, proficiency in logistics-related knowledge and skills from suppliers, and the adoption of environmentally friendly logistics solutions. Whitlock et.al (2021), examined the application of Building Information Modeling (BIM) in construction logistics management (CLM). BIM, a digital representation process throughout a project's lifecycle, gains a temporal dimension in 4D BIM, allowing simulation of the construction process over time. Jing Liu and Ming Lu (2018) proposed a constraint programming (CP) approach to optimize project schedules under material logistics and crew availability constraints. The CP approach effectively handles complex constraints and discrete decision variables, with the authors developing a model considering material delivery times, crew availability, and activity precedence relationships. Applied to a case study, the CP model demonstrates its ability to generate near-optimal schedules minimizing project duration and cost. Mahdi and Haider (2022), explores the classic optimization problem of the transportation problem and its various solution methods, including Vogel's approximation, the North-West corner method, and the stepping-stone method. They introduce the NOOR1 method, emphasizing its use of decomposition to break down the transportation problem into smaller, more manageable subproblems. Tunji et al(2017), explores the impact of logistics factors on material procurement. The authors conducted a quantitative study using questionnaires distributed to contractors in Abuja, Nigeria, analyzing the data with descriptive and inferential statistics. Logistics factors significantly affect material procurement, including late deliveries, inaccurate forecasts, delivery errors, transportation challenges, waiting times, and poor material quality. Vendor quality and procurement officer competence emerge as crucial elements for successful material procurement. The literature review highlights the significance of logistics optimization in various domains, including road construction projects, modular integrated construction (MIC), warehouse and inventory management, construction logistics management (CLM) through Building Information Modeling (BIM), and the transportation problem. Previous studies identify drawbacks such as high logistics costs in construction projects, the need for integrated logistics planning in MIC projects, challenges in warehouse and inventory management, the application of 4D BIM in CLM, and various methods for solving the transportation problem. This study aims to address these drawbacks by proposing a comprehensive approach to logistics optimization. Drawing from the insights of previous works, it aims to overcome challenges by integrating linear programming models for road construction. The study seeks to provide a holistic understanding of logistics optimization, offering practical solutions to enhance efficiency and reduce costs of transportation.

Objectives of the study

1. To identify and rank the factors which affects logistics management during highway construction
2. To perform Factor Analysis by using SPSS software.
3. To developing mathematical Linear Programming model for transportation problems.
4. To solve the LP model by using Conventional Operational Research methods (VAM&MODI) and CPLEX software

Methodology

To understand more specifically let's consider a case study of highway construction and figure out the factors that affects the logistics management. The typical technique of conducting a questionnaire survey was used to get respondents' perspectives on the factors affecting the logistics management during highway construction. The questionnaire survey was distributed to the Civil Engineers, Planning In-charges, Project Managers, academics, researchers, and students. Participants were asked to include any extra factors and provide a rating (weightage) based on their experience for all the factors affecting Logistics management. There are 20 factors for the questionnaire and 5 point Likert scale was used to rate the responses with a rating of 5 for very Important, 4 for Important, 3 for Moderately Important, 2 -for Slightly Important, 1 for Very Least Important.

Frequency index

$$FI = \frac{\sum A(n)}{5N}$$

Where

A = constant expressing the weight assigned to each response (Ranging 1 for very least important and 5 for very important)
 n = frequency of each response and
 N = Total number of responses.

SPSS:

The SPSS analysis for Likert data encompasses systematic procedures that enable researchers to gain a comprehensive understanding of participant perspectives, fostering insightful interpretations and informed decision-making based on the acquired survey responses.

Methodology Flowchart

Fig 1: Methodology flowchart

Factors affecting Logistics Management

The following 20 factors affecting logistics management were found from a review of the literature.

1. Location of camp, offices and plants
2. Storage and warehousing
3. To plan for timely material supply
4. Efficient allocation and maintenance of equipment
5. Effective Transportation of materials
6. Proper vehicle routing and traffic management
7. Maintain optimal stock levels.
8. Utilization of Technology and resource optimization tools
9. Monitoring and controlling logistics costs.
10. Project Scheduling: Create a detailed construction schedule.
11. Lead Time: Lead time from source to destination
12. Project duration
13. Labor Management: Recruiting and training
14. Design Changes: Adapt logistics to accommodate design modifications.
15. Communication: Establishing effective stakeholder communication

- 16. Quality Control: Ensure material adherence to specifications.
- 17. Environmental Clearances and Regulations
- 18. Disruptions due to weather
- 19. Safety: Prioritize safety for all personnel and road users.
- 20. Risk Management: Preparedness for unforeseen events

Process of Logistics Management in highway construction flowchart:

Fig 2: Process of Logistics Management in highway construction.

A total of 160 questionnaire surveys were sent by email and in person to civil engineers, project managers, professors, researchers, and students. The survey received 104 responses from a total of 160 participants. The response rate was 65%, which was satisfactory because a response rate of more than 40% is considered acceptable.

Data Analysis The data analysis is performed for two purposes ranking and factor analysis. In this data, the ranking of factors is crucial for understanding the relative importance of different elements. A higher rank indicates greater perceived significance, while a lower rank suggests lower importance. Analyzing the order of factors allows to focus on addressing or emphasizing the most influential aspects, aiding in targeted decision-making. Additionally, it provides valuable insights for prioritizing interventions or improvements based on the perceived impact of each factor. Monitoring and controlling logistics costs, to plan for timely material supply, Project Scheduling, Effective Transportation of materials are the crucial factors which needs to be focused more.

Factor Analysis Factor analysis in SPSS is a statistical method used to identify underlying factors or dimensions within a set of observed variables. It helps simplify data by grouping correlated variables into common factors, aiding in the interpretation of complex relationships. SPSS provides tools for extracting factors, assessing their significance, and interpreting their impact on the observed variables. Researchers use factor analysis to uncover latent structures and reduce data complexity for more meaningful insights.

Table 1: Frequency Index for the factors affecting logistics management

Factors Affecting Logistics Management	FI	Rank
Monitoring and controlling logistics costs.	0.838462	1
Quality Control: Ensure material adherence to specifications.	0.834615	2
To plan for timely material supply	0.823077	3
Effective Transportation of materials	0.819231	4
Project Scheduling: Create a detailed construction schedule.	0.819231	4
Efficient allocation and maintenance of equipment	0.815385	5
Location of camp, offices and plants	0.807692	6
Safety: Prioritize safety for all personnel and road users.	0.796154	7
Communication: Establishing effective stakeholder communication	0.788462	8
Proper vehicle routing and traffic management	0.784615	9
Storage and warehousing	0.784615	10
Utilization of Technology and resource optimization tools	0.780769	11
Project duration	0.780769	11
Risk Management: Preparedness for unforeseen events.	0.780769	12
Lead Time: Lead time from source to destination	0.773077	13
Maintain optimal stock levels.	0.769231	14
Environmental Clearances and Regulations	0.769231	14
Labor Management: Recruiting and training	0.765385	15
Design Changes: Adapt logistics to accommodate design modifications.	0.757692	16
Disruptions due to weather	0.742308	17

Table 2: SPSS output for KMO and Bartlett's test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.873
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2012.503
	df	190
	Sig.	0.000

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure assesses the adequacy of a dataset for factor analysis, with values closer to 1 indicating better suitability. Typically, a KMO value above 0.6 is considered acceptable. On the other hand, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity evaluates whether correlations between variables are significant for factor analysis. A small p-value (usually

below 0.05) in Bartlett's test suggests substantial correlations, supporting the meaningful application of factor analysis. Both KMO and Bartlett's test serve as crucial diagnostics to ensure the reliability and validity of factor analysis results, helping researchers make informed decisions about the appropriateness of the data for this statistical technique.

Table 3: SPSS output for Total Variance

Total Variance									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	11.831	59.154	59.154	11.831	59.154	59.154	4.94	24.713	24.713
2	1.222	6.110	65.264	1.222	6.110	65.264	4.21	21.033	45.746
3	1.077	5.383	70.648	1.077	5.383	70.648	3.76	18.778	64.524
4	1.043	5.217	75.865	1.043	5.217	75.865	2.27	11.341	75.865

The prominent factors revealed in this study demonstrate a favorable quality, each encompassing at least three variables per factor, as suggested by Yong and Pearce (2013). Loading values below 0.550 were excluded from the analysis for precision because it indicates weak correlations, suggesting that those variables are less relevant or contribute less to the identified factors. The factors were subsequently named by taking into account the underlying causes associated with each factor. This approach ensures a robust identification of meaningful and relevant factors in the study.

Developing mathematical Linear Programming model for transportation problem

From the rankings, it is evident that transportation is one the critical factor for efficient logistics management. Hence we take the highway construction case study to formulate the mathematical linear programming model for transportation problem and solve with different methods to get cost effective model. Considering to transport concrete from two origins to different destinations required. Let's find out the best suitable method for the explained scenario.

Transportation Problem

A type of linear programming problem specifically designed to determine the most cost-effective or profit-maximizing way to distribute goods from multiple sources (supply points) to multiple destinations (demand points).

It involves variables like:

- Supply at each source
- Demand at each destination
- Cost or profit associated with transporting goods between each source-destination pair

The objective is usually to minimize total transportation cost or maximize total profit.

Distribution Matrix

A tabular representation of the transportation problem, used to organize and visualize the relevant data. It has a row for each source and a column for each destination. The cells in the matrix represent the cost or profit of transporting a unit of goods from a particular source to a particular destination. It also includes supply and demand values in the rightmost column and bottommost row, respectively. The mathematical statement of a transportation problem involves defining the objective function, decision variables, and constraints.

Table 4: Sample Transportation Problem Matrix

	Destination 1		Destination 2		Destination 3		Destination 4		Supply
Source 1	X11		X12		X13		X14		A1
		C11		C12		C13		C14	
Source 2	X21		X22		X23		X24		A2
		C21		C22		C23		C24	
Source 3	X31		X32		X33		X34		A3
		C31		C32		C33		X34	
Demand	B1		B2		B3		B4		

Objective Function

The objective function represents the goal of the transportation problem, which is typically to minimize total transportation costs or maximize total profits. It is expressed mathematically as:

$$\text{Minimize } Z = \sum \sum C_{ij} X_{ij}$$

where:

Z is the total transportation cost or profit

C_{ij} is the cost or profit per unit of goods transported from source i to destination j

X_{ij} is the quantity of goods transported from source i to destination j

Decision Variables The decision variables represent the quantities of goods to be transported from each source to each destination. They are denoted as X_{ij} , where i represents the source and j represents the destination.

Constraints The constraints represent the supply and demand limitations. The supply constraints ensure that the total quantity of goods shipped from each source does not exceed its available supply. The demand constraints ensure that the total quantity of goods received at each destination meets the required demand.

Vogels Approximation method

1. Penalty Calculation: Compute penalties by finding differences between the two smallest costs in each row and column.
2. Identify Highest Penalty: Determine the row or column with the highest penalty, breaking ties based on the smallest minimum cost.
3. Allocate Minimum Cost Cell: Allocate units to the cell with the minimum transportation cost in the identified row or column.
4. Update Supply and Demand: Adjust supply and demand values by subtracting allocated units; eliminate rows or columns with zero supply or demand.
5. Iterative Process: Repeat the process iteratively until all supply and demand values are reduced to zero.
6. Optimality Check: Verify optimality by ensuring all supply and demand constraints are satisfied; if not, return to the penalty calculation step.
7. Interpretation: Interpret the final solution in terms of transportation flow, considering allocated units and associated costs. Vogel's Approximation Method provides an efficient initial solution for transportation problems.

Table 5: Transportation Problem Matrix

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	Supply
Batching Plant 1	24	25	20	18	18	17	592
Batching Plant 2	17	18	19	21	27	22	592
Demand	23	93	290	115	185	556	

Mathematical Linear Programming Model for the Transportation Problem

Decision Variables X_{ij} : Quantity of product transported from Batching Plant i to Destination j ($i=1,2; j=1,2,\dots,6$)

Objective Function Minimize $Z = 24x_{11} + 25x_{12} + 20x_{13} + 18x_{14} + 18x_{15} + 17x_{16} + 17x_{21} + 18x_{22} + 19x_{23} + 21x_{24} + 27x_{25} + 22x_{26}$

Constraints

Supply Constraints

Total quantity of product shipped from each Batching Plant cannot exceed its available supply

$$x_{11} + x_{12} + x_{13} + x_{14} + x_{15} + x_{16} \leq 592 \text{ (for Batching Plant 1)}$$

$$x_{21} + x_{22} + x_{23} + x_{24} + x_{25} + x_{26} \leq 592 \text{ (for Batching Plant 2)}$$

Demand Constraints

Total quantity of product received at each Destination must meet its demand.

$$x_{11} + x_{21} \geq 23 \text{ (for Destination 1)}$$

$$x_{12} + x_{22} \geq 93 \text{ (for Destination 2)}$$

$$x_{13} + x_{23} \geq 290 \text{ (for Destination 3)}$$

$$x_{14} + x_{24} \geq 115 \text{ (for Destination 4)}$$

$$x_{15} + x_{25} \geq 185 \text{ (for Destination 5)}$$

$$x_{16} + x_{26} \geq 556 \text{ (for Destination 6)}$$

Non-negativity Constraints

Quantity of product transported cannot be negative

$$x_{ij} \geq 0 \text{ for all } i \text{ and } j.$$

Table 6: Transportation Problem solution by using VAM after 8 iterations

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	Supply
Batching Plant 1	24	25	20	18	185	17	592
Batching Plant 2	17	18	19	21	27	22	592
Batching Plant 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	83
Demand	23	93	290	115	185	556	

Total Minimum Cost

$$= (83 \times 0 + 185 \times 18 + 28 \times 17 + 93 \times 18 + 407 \times 17 + 149 \times 22 + 115 \times 21 + 207 \times 19)$$

$$= 22025$$

Modified Distribution Method(MODI) method

1. Create a matrix with costs, supply (rows), and demand (columns).
2. Initial Solution: Choose North-West Corner, Least Cost, or Vogel's method to get an initial feasible allocation.
3. Calculate Penalties: For empty cells, find the sum of its cost and lowest allocations in its row and column (penalties).
4. Find Most Negative Penalty: Identify the empty cell with the lowest (most negative) penalty.
5. Form Closed Loop: Create a loop starting from the chosen cell, alternating between row and column with smallest allocations, until returning.
6. Allocate Quantity: Transfer the maximum allowable quantity (min (supply, demand, empty cell capacity)) to the chosen cell, adjusting loop allocations to maintain constraints.
7. Repeat: Update penalties, find the most negative one, form a loop, and allocate until all penalties are non-negative (optimal solution found).

Table 7: Transportation Problem solution by using MODI after 9 iterations

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	Supply
Batching Plant 1	24	25	20	18	18	17	592
Batching Plant 2	17	18	19	21	27	22	592
Batching Plant 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	83
Demand	23	93	290	115	185	556	

Total Minimum Cost

$$= (18 \times 102 + 17 \times 490 + 17 \times 28 + 18 \times 93 + 19 \times 290 + 21 \times 115 + 22 \times 66 + 0 \times 83)$$

$$= 21693$$

Cplex Software IBM ILOG CPLEX Optimization Studio is a powerful tool for solving optimization problems, including transportation problems. CPLEX stands for IBM ILOG CPLEX Optimization Studio. Here are the general steps to solve a transportation problem using CPLEX.

1. Formulate the Model: Define the decision variables, objective function, and constraints of your transportation problem.
2. Install and Set Up CPLEX: Ensure that CPLEX is installed and properly set up on your system. You can use CPLEX through various interfaces like the CPLEX Interactive Optimizer, CPLEX Concert Technology (C++, Java, or .NET APIs), or Python.
3. Define Decision Variables and Objective Function: Use CPLEX APIs or modeling languages to define decision variables and the objective function. Specify whether you want to minimize or maximize the objective.
4. Specify Constraints: Define constraints such as supply and demand constraints using CPLEX APIs or modelling languages.
5. Set Solver Options: Configure solver options, such as the optimization method, time limit, or tolerance levels, based on the requirements of your transportation problem.
6. Optimize the Model: Instruct CPLEX to solve the optimization problem by calling the appropriate function or method. This might be the solve function in C++, the solve () method in Java, or the solve() method in Python.
7. Retrieve and Interpret Results: Retrieve the optimal solution and objective value from the CPLEX output. Interpret the results to understand the optimal allocation of goods and associated costs.
8. Post-Processing (Optional): Depending on your specific requirements, you might need to perform additional post-processing of the results obtained from CPLEX.

Fig 1: Output of LP Transportation model by using CPLEX

From the CPLEX software it is obvious that it is short of 83 units and with available supply the demand satisfies with Rs.21693 which is similar to MODI approach.

Table 8: Comparison of VAM, MODI and CPLEX software

Feature	VAM (Vogel's Approximation Method)	Modi Method	CPLEX Software
Type	Heuristic	Iterative, manual method	Optimization software
Complexity	Low	Medium	High
Ease of Use	Very easy, quick initial solution	Moderate, requires manual calculations and loop manipulation	Complex, requires software installation and learning curve
Accuracy	Approximate, not guaranteed to be optimal	Guaranteed optimal solution in most cases	Extremely accurate, finds the absolute optimal solution
Suitability	Small to medium problems, quick estimations	Small to medium problems, initial solution for Modi Method	Large and complex problems with numerous variables and constraints
Speed	Very fast, simple calculations	Moderate, depends on iterations	Very fast, optimized algorithms for solving large problems
Flexibility	Limited, only for basic transportation problems	Limited, manual method not easily adaptable to diverse constraints	Highly flexible, handles various LP problem types and complex constraints
Cost	Free, no software required	Free, no software required	Requires purchasing or licensing the software

Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings derived from the questionnaire study emphasize the paramount importance of four key factors for maintaining effective logistics during highway construction. These factors include the meticulous monitoring and control of logistics costs, strategic planning for timely material supply, efficient project scheduling, and the effective transportation of materials. The research also highlights the significance of utilizing advanced tools for solving transportation problems, comparing the CPLEX software with traditional methods such as VAM and MODI. The results indicate that, in contrast to VAM and MODI, which may require more iterations to address transportation problems, the CPLEX software emerged as an exceptionally helpful and effective tool. Its efficiency in handling problems with numerous variables was notable, showcasing its superiority in optimizing supply and demand scenarios. Consequently, based on the research outcomes, it can be concluded that CPLEX stands out as the preferred and most efficient tool for solving transportation problems in the context of highway construction logistics. This conclusion underscores the potential of advanced optimization tools to significantly enhance the overall effectiveness of logistics management in construction projects.

References

1. Caron, F., Marchet, G., & Perego, A. (1998), "Project logistics: integrating the procurement and construction processes", *International journal of project management*, 16: 311-319.
2. Alvanchi, A., Baniassadi, F., Shahsavari, M., & Kashani, H. (2021), "Improving materials logistics plan in road construction projects using discrete event simulation", *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 28: 3144-3163.
3. Uzorh, A., & Innocent, N. (2014), "Supply chain management optimization problem", *The International Journal of Engineering and Science (IJES)*, 6:1-9.
4. Dubois, A., Hulthén, K., & Sundquist, V. (2019), "Organising logistics and transport activities in construction", *The international journal of logistics management*, 30:620-640.
5. Yong, A. G., & Pearce, S. (2013), "A beginner's guide to factor analysis: Focusing on exploratory factor analysis", *Tutorials in quantitative methods for psychology*, 9:79-94.
6. Wijekoon, S. B., & Attanayake, A. M. C. T. K. (2012). Study on the cost overruns in road construction projects in Sri Lanka.
7. Williams, B., Brown, T. and Onsmann, A. (2010), "Exploratory factor analysis: A five-step guide for novices", *Australian Journal of Paramedicine*, 8: 1-13.
8. Akoa, B.B. (2011). Cost overruns and time delays in highway and bridge projects in developing countries - experiences from Cameroon. MS diss., Michigan State University.
9. Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. (2011), "Making sense of Cronbach's alpha", *International journal of medical education*, 2:53.
10. Choudhari, S. and Tindwani, A. (2017), "Logistics optimisation in road construction project", *Construction Innovation*, 17:158-179.
11. Chandrasekaran Balaji Venkateswaran and Rajiah Murugasan. (2017), "Time delay and cost overrun of road over bridge (ROB) construction projects in India", *Journal of Construction in Developing Countries*, 22: 79-96.
12. Chotechoei, N. (2018), "Factors affecting the efficiency of logistics management of small and medium enterprises in Thailand: A case study of logistics service providers", *PSAKU International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 7.
13. CPLEX User's Guide" by IBM ILOG CPLEX Division (2023)
14. Daugherty, P. J. (2011), "Review of logistics and supply chain relationship literature and suggested research agenda", *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 41:16-31.
15. Niu, S., Yang, Y., & Pan, W. (2019), "Logistics planning and visualization of modular integrated construction projects based on BIM-GIS integration and vehicle routing algorithm", *Modular and Offsite Construction (MOC) Summit Proceedings*, 579-586.
16. Jing Liu and Ming Lu. "Constraint Programming Approach to Optimizing Project Schedules under Material Logistics and Crew Availability Constraints", *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 144:040180492
17. Mahdi and Haider (2022), "The New Technique for Solving Transportation Problem", *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, 7:1-10
18. Patience F.Tunji-Olayeni, Adedeji O. Afolabi, Rapheal A. Ojelabi and Beatrice A Ayim, (2017), "Impact of Logistics Factors on Material Procurement for Construction Projects", *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 8:1142-1148.
19. Ghourrassi, A., & Tigu, G. (2017), "The relationship between logistics management and customer satisfaction", *Journal of Business Economics & Management*, 18:1023-1034.
20. Whitlock, K., Abanda, F. H., Manjia, M. B., Pettang, C., & Nkeng, G. E. (2021), "4D BIM for construction logistics management", *CivilEng*, 2:325-348.